

VNS APPROACH FOR TOTAL TARDINESS MINIMIZATION IN A SINGLE MACHINE SCHEDULING PROBLEM WITH PERIODIC RESOURCE CONSTRAINTS

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Abstract: *In this paper, we consider a recently introduced variant of a single machine scheduling problem with periodical resource constraints. The goal is to minimize the total tardiness of all jobs that need to be scheduled on a single machine, taking into account the time and resource consumption constraints per production period. Since the considered problem is NP-hard, we propose a metaheuristic approach using the Variable neighborhood search (VNS). The performance of the VNS method is evaluated on a set of test instances from the literature with up to 1000 jobs. The obtained results are compared with the results of other methods from the literature and show the efficiency of the proposed VNS approach over the other algorithms.*

Keywords: *Combinatorial optimization, Metaheuristics, Variable neighborhood search, Scheduling problems, Single machine, Resource consumption, Tardiness.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Scheduling problems have received considerable attention for many years. In the general case, the task is to schedule the execution of n jobs on m machines under certain conditions and constraints. These are real-life factors such as machine failure during operation, delay in starting machine operation, pre-emption, time constraints to be met, resource constraints (e.g. financial budget, material quantity), etc. In the case where $m=1$, the task is reduced to scheduling jobs on a single machine, and several variants of this problem have been studied in the literature in recent decades (Bai et al., 2020; Cui and Lu, 2017; Karhi and Shabtay, 2018). Despite the simplicity of their formulation, these problems usually belong to the class of the most difficult (NP-hard) discrete optimization problems, even in the case of a single machine. The most common objectives of these problems are to minimize the total time for the execution of all jobs, to minimize the total time during which the machines are actively working, to minimize the total delay when the jobs are not executed on time, etc. Tardiness has a negative impact on profitability and therefore needs to be minimized. It leads to a loss of reputation with customers and reduces the possibility of attracting new customers. In addition, tardiness usually leads to late payments and penalties, resulting in additional operating costs. Some of the many scheduling problems that take tardiness into account can be found in (Chen, 2006; Gupta and Smith, 2006; Herr and Goel, 2016).

In this paper, we consider a variant of a single-machine scheduling problem with periodic resource constraints (SMPRC) with the objective of minimizing the total tardiness. In the classical SMPRC, there is a single machine environment with multiple production periods. Each period has a duration of fixed time units (e.g. working day or week) and in each period there is a fixed resource constraint that limits resource consumption. The goal is to minimize the makespan, i.e. the total time required to complete all jobs. The classical SMPRC was introduced in the paper, where the authors proved that the problem is NP-hard, described it as a mixed-integer linear programming problem (MILP) and presented the solutions of the problem obtained using 22 different methods. The Variable neighborhood search for solving the same problem was proposed in. In the paper, the authors presented the new variant of SMPRC with an objective function that minimizes the total tardiness. The authors developed a MILP model for the addressed variant of the problem and presented two matheuristics as solution methods: matheuristic Size Reduction with Simulated Annealing (SRSA) and matheuristic Relax-and-Fix with Variable Fixing Search (RFVFS).

Given the NP-hard nature and complexity of the problem, a metaheuristic approach is employed. In particular, we propose a Variable Neighborhood Search (VNS) method, selected for its simplicity and previously demonstrated success in solving related scheduling problems. The elements of the proposed VNS have been specifically adapted to address the structure and constraints of the considered problem variant, including

appropriate modifications of the neighborhood structures to ensure alignment with the problem's requirements. Furthermore, the computational results demonstrate that the proposed VNS outperforms existing methods on a variety of test instances from the literature, confirming its effectiveness and practical applicability.

This paper is organized as follows. In the second chapter a description of the problem is given. The third chapter describes the Variable neighborhood search method proposed to solve this problem. The computational results obtained and their comparison with previous results from the literature are presented in Chapter 4. Chapter 5 contains conclusions and suggestions for further research.

2. PROBLEM DEFINITION

The SMPRC with total tardiness can be described as follows. At time zero, there are n jobs J_1, \dots, J_n that need to be processed on a single machine. Each job J_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$ requires the processing time p_i , the amount of resources r_i and should ideally be completed before its due date d_i . The total available time is divided into limited time periods/blocks (e.g. weekdays) of length P . For each time block, there is a maximum amount of available resources R , and the resources that are not used in one block cannot be used in another. In general, P is not sufficient to process all jobs and it is assumed that $P \geq p_i$ and $R \geq r_i$ for all $i = 1, \dots, n$. All jobs must be produced on a single machine, which cannot process more than one job at a time. Interruptions in the production process are not allowed, i.e. it is not allowed to start the production of a job in one time block and finish it in another. In this variant of a problem, the due dates d_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$ are determined as the serial number (index) of a block period by which the job i should ideally be completed. If we denote with C_i the index of a time block in which a product i was produced, then its tardiness can be calculated as $T_i = \max\{0, C_i - d_i\}$. The goal is to schedule the production of all jobs to the time blocks in such a way that the total tardiness for all jobs $\sum_{i=1}^n T_i$ is minimized.

An illustrative example with 7 jobs, $p = \{4, 4, 3, 3, 2, 2, 1\}$, $r = \{4, 3, 2, 3, 3, 1, 1\}$, $d = \{3, 3, 1, 1, 2, 2, 1\}$, $P = 8$ and $R = 6$ is shown in Figure 1. For two different schedules $x_1 = \{1, 3, 2, 4, 5, 6, 7\}$ and $x_2 = \{3, 4, 7, 2, 5, 6, 1\}$ the Gantt chart diagrams for processing the jobs in these orders are shown. Figure 1a shows the optimal solution of SMPRC with the objective of minimizing the makespan. For a given job order, all jobs are scheduled in 3 blocks, and the time required to complete the entire process is 21 time units. Note that although J_7 requires only 1 time unit ($p_7 = 1$) and there is enough free time in the first two blocks, it cannot be scheduled there because both blocks have used up all the resources allocated to them. In this solution, the completion and tardiness vectors are given by $C = \{1, 2, 1, 2, 3, 3, 3\}$ and $T = \{0, 0, 0, 1, 1, 1, 2\}$, and thus the total tardiness for this schedule is 5. Figure 1b shows the optimal solution of SMPRC with the objective of minimizing the total tardiness. In this case, the vectors for completion time blocks and tardiness are $C = \{3, 2, 1, 1, 2, 3, 1\}$ and $T = \{0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 0\}$. For this schedule, all jobs are also scheduled in 3 time blocks, the makespan is 22, but the objective of total tardiness is reduced to 1.

3. THE PROPOSED VARIABLE NEIGHBORHOOD SEARCH

The VNS metaheuristic originally proposed by Mladenovic and Hansen (Mladenović and Hansen, 1997) is based on the idea of systematically changing the neighborhood structures in order to escape from a possible local optimum. The basic variant of the VNS method consists of two phases that alternate together with the neighborhood change step until a stopping criterion is met. The first phase, called Shaking, is used to escape from local optimal solutions. The second phase is the Local search phase, in which some neighborhood of the solution obtained in the Shaking phase is explored in order to reach a local optimum. The VNS method has already been successfully used to solve many difficult optimization and scheduling problems. For example, VNS heuristics have been developed for scheduling problems with multiple machines (Adibi et al., 2010; Ahmadian et al., 2021; Wang and Li, 2014), as well as for single machine problems (Liao and Cheng, 2007; Pacheco et al., 2018).

Algorithm 1 presents pseudocode of the proposed VNS algorithm for the SCPRC with minimizing tardiness. The solution of the problem is represented by an integer vector x of length n with unique integer values $1 \leq x_k \leq n$, $x_i \neq x_j$ which represent the order in which the jobs will be executed on the machine. The algorithm starts by generating an initial solution which is a random permutation of integers from 1 to n , representing the indices of the jobs.

Within a VNS main loop, the shaking procedure, the local search procedure and the neighborhood change step are applied alternately. For a given k , the neighborhood $N_k(x)$ contains all vectors with job indices that may differ from the current solution x in at most k index positions. The Shaking() function generates a new vector $x' \in N_k(x)$ following the next steps. First, a vector of k random integers from 1 to n is formed. This vector represents the indices of the solution vector x that are to be changed. The values at the selected positions are

(a) SMPRC with minimizing makespan

(b) SMPRC with minimizing total tardiness

Figure 1: Comparison of the optimal solutions for SMPRC with minimizing (a) makespan, (b) total tardiness

Algorithm 1 VNS Algorithm

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1: procedure VNS ALGORITHM( $n, k_{\min}, k_{\max}, t_{\max}, prob$ )
2:    $x \leftarrow$  RandomPermutation( $1, n$ )
3:    $t \leftarrow$  CpuTime()
4:   while  $t \leq t_{\max}$  do
5:      $k \leftarrow k_{\min}$ 
6:     while  $k \leq k_{\max}$  do
7:        $x' \leftarrow$  Shaking( $x, k$ )
8:        $x'' \leftarrow$  LocalSearch( $x'$ )
9:       if ObjectiveFunction( $x''$ ) < ObjectiveFunction( $x$ ) then
10:         $x \leftarrow x''$ 
11:       else
12:         if ObjectiveFunction( $x''$ ) > ObjectiveFunction( $x$ ) then
13:           $k \leftarrow k + 1$ 
14:         else
15:           if RandomProbability() <  $prob$  then
16:             $x \leftarrow x''$ 
17:           else
18:             $k \leftarrow k + 1$ 
19:           end if
20:         end if
21:       end if
22:     end while
23:      $t \leftarrow$  CpuTime()
24:   end while
25:   return  $x$ 
26: end procedure

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shifted cyclically by one position to the left, with the first value being shifted to the last position. This direction of rotation was chosen because it can be assumed that the tardiness of all but one of the selected jobs can be reduced when they are moved forwards. The values at the unselected positions remain unchanged. This is illustrated in Figure 2 using a small example.

Figure 2: An example of shaking a solution vector of length 8, for $k = 3$

The LocalSearch() function explores the neighborhood of a solution x' in order to find a new solution with a smaller objective function value. The neighborhood to be explored consists of all solutions obtained from x' by swapping two of its elements. The first improvement strategy is used. The local search stops when the solution can no longer be improved and the best solution is denoted by x'' .

Finally, it should be decided whether a new solution x'' should be accepted or not. If the local optimum x'' is better than the current solution x , the algorithm moves to this new solution and continues the search in the same neighborhood N_k . If the solution x'' is worse than x , the search is continued from the same x in the next neighborhood $N_{k+1}(x)$. Since the solution is represented as a permutation of jobs, there are various feasible sequences that lead to the same objective function value. For example, all jobs from the same block can change their position, leading to different solutions with the same objective function value. In such cases, where the problem has many local minima with the same objective function value, moving from one to another can expand the search and increase the chances of finding a better solution. On the other hand, there is a risk of being trapped in cycles if this step is performed every time. To avoid these problems, the solution x'' with the same objective function as x is accepted with a given probability *prob* and rejected with probability $1 - prob$. The VNS finishes its work once the maximum allowed CPU time, which is defined by the parameter t_{\max} , is reached.

4. EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

The VNS metaheuristic for solving the problem under consideration is implemented in the C programming language. The computational experiments were performed on a desktop computer with Intel Core i7-11700 3.6GHz processor and 16GB RAM in a 64bit Windows 10 environment. The experimental results were obtained on a set of 50 instances from the literature with up to 1000 jobs from (B. Prata et al., 2022). For each test instance, VNS was executed 10 times, each time starting from a different random initial solution. The VNS parameters were set to $k_{\min} = 2, k_{\max} = 10, t_{\max} = n$ and $prob = 0.4$.

In accordance with the experimental setup used in (B. Prata et al., 2022), the stopping criterion was defined as a fixed time limit of $t_{\max} = n$ seconds per run, where n is the number of jobs in the instance. This ensures that the algorithm runs proportionally to the problem size, enabling a meaningful comparison across different instance sizes. For example, an instance with 50 jobs was executed for 50 seconds, while an instance with 1000 jobs was allotted 1000 seconds.

The results of the proposed VNS were compared with the results of a MILP model and a hybrid matheuristic SRSA also presented in (B. Prata et al., 2022). Although the authors developed one more heuristic (RSVFS) in this paper, we did not have the solutions for RSVFS, so we only present the results of the comparison with the results of MILP and SRSA. The Relative Deviation Index (*RDI*) is used to compare the results obtained with these methods. Let H be the set of solution methods and T_{st} the best solution obtained with a method $s \in H$ for the instance t . RDI_{st} for the method $s \in H$ when solving the instance t is calculated as

$$RDI_{st} = \frac{T_{st} - \min_{h \in H} T_{ht}}{\min_{h \in H} T_{ht}}.$$

Table 1 shows for each of the compared methods $s \in \{MILP, SRSA, VNS\}$ the average values of RDI calculated over the set of instances with the same dimension $n \in \{50, 100, 250, 500, 1000\}$. Each instance group consists of 10 instances of the same dimension. The first column of the table contains the name of the method, while the following columns contain the average RDI values for all instances of the specified dimension in that set. The best values are in bold.

Table 1: Average values of RDI for MILP, SRSA and VNS

Method / Dimension	50	100	250	500	1000
MILP	0.65	3.24	3.94	9.97	12.74
SRSA	2.60	3.47	0.12	2.73	25.97
VNS	0	0	2.12	0.54	0

A comparison of the results presented in Table 1 shows that the VNS method achieves the best results according to this criterion in 4 out of 5 instance sets (test instances with 50, 100, 500 and 1000 jobs). In the case of the instance set with $n = 250$ VNS performs worse than SRSA, but better than MILP. Note that if the average RDI value in the table is 0, that means that the method under consideration has achieved the best known results for all instances from that group. This is the case for VNS and instance sets with 50, 100 and 1000 jobs.

Table 2 shows, for each set of 10 instances with the same dimensions, the total number of instances for which the MILP, SRSA and VNS methods achieved the best value $\min_{h \in H} T_{hr}$. The results are consistent with those of the RDI comparison. VNS achieves the highest number of best solutions for 50, 100, 500 and 1000 jobs, while in the case of $n = 250$ the SRSA method achieves the best solution for 9 out of 10 instances, VNS for only one instance and MILP for none.

Table 2: Total number of attained best known values for MILP, SRSA and VNS

Method / Dimension	50	100	250	500	1000
MILP	4	0	0	1	0
SRSA	1	0	9	4	0
VNS	10	10	1	5	10

Since the VNS method was executed 10 times for each instance, Table 3 shows the quality of the solutions obtained. For each set of 10 instances of the same dimension, the first row (labeled err_{avg}) shows the average value of the percentage relative error of the solutions obtained with the VNS method and the second row shows the average value of the standard deviation (σ_{avg}).

Table 3: Average values of computation time, percentual relative error and standard deviation for 10 executions of VNS

Parameter / Dimension	50	100	250	500	1000
err_{avg}	0.15	1.04	2.29	2.10	1.41
σ_{avg}	0.15	0.76	1.40	1.09	0.83

Only for the smallest instance set with 50 jobs VNS showed a constant performance and achieved the best solution for 9 out of 10 instances in all 10 runs. As the dimension of the instances increases, the number of solutions that are not the same (and best) in 10 runs increases for VNS. The worst performance is for instance set with 250 jobs, where err_{avg} and σ_{avg} have the highest values.

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we consider a variant of a single-machine scheduling problem with periodic resource constraints with the objective of minimizing the total tardiness. Since the considered problem is NP-hard, the Variable neighborhood search metaheuristic is proposed. The obtained VNS results were compared with the results of two methods (MILP, SRSA) from the literature. On average, the proposed VNS method achieves better results than other proposed methods from the literature in most cases. Future research is related to the introduction of new neighborhood, the acceleration of the local search procedure with additional adaptations of the components of the proposed method according to the characteristics of the problem under consideration, and the hybridization of the proposed method with other heuristics to solve this problem.

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